

FACTORS OF FORMATION OF CRITICAL THINKING IN FUTURE MODERN
TEACHERS

Master's student of Bukhara State Pedagogical Institute:

Nematova Nigina Nabiyevna

90.339-45-97

Academic supervisor: Bukhara State Pedagogical Institute Doctor of Pedagogical Sciences
(DSc), Professor:

G.V.Izbullayeva

Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada tanqidiy fikrlash ko'nikmasi haqida mazmun –mohiyati haqida xorijiy va mahalliy olimlarning qarashlari atroflicha izohlangan. Tanqidiy fikrlashni ko'nikmasini bo'lajak o'qituvchilarda shakllantirish omillari, bilish va o'rganish faoliyatining tanqidiy fikrlash ko'nikmasi bilan bog'liqlik jihatlari yoritib berilgan.

Abstract: In this article, the views of foreign and local scientists about the content and essence of the skill of critical thinking are detailed. Factors of formation of critical thinking skills in future teachers, aspects of knowledge and learning activities related to critical thinking skills are explained.

Аннотация: В данной статье подробно изложены взгляды зарубежных и отечественных ученых на содержание и сущность навыка критического мышления. Объяснены факторы формирования навыков критического мышления у будущих учителей, аспекты познания и учебной деятельности, связанные с навыками критического мышления.

Kalit so'zlar: Innovatsion, kompetensiya, ta'lim-tarbiya jarayoni, fikrlash, tanqidiy fikrlash, mantiqiy fikrlash, vaqt, izn, rang-baranglik, qadrlash, qimmatchilik.

Key words: Innovation, competence, educational process, thinking, critical thinking, logical thinking, time, resolution, variety, evaluation, value.

Ключевые слова: Инновация, компетентность, образовательный процесс, мышление, критическое мышление, логическая мышление, время, разрешение, разнообразие, оценка, ценность.

Developments taking place in the material and spiritual spheres of modern social existence are reflected in changes in human thinking, thinking, and worldview. Developing the cognitive activity of students in organizing the educational process, improving the ability of independent and critical thinking, preparing future teachers for modern, innovative activities remains an urgent problem.

Interactive methods have been created as a result of many scientific and practical works on the use of modern pedagogical technologies that guarantee efficiency in the educational system of developed countries. , we can observe that the development of the aspects of independent problem solving was the basis for the formation of abilities such as being able to look at every change with critical thinking.

The ability to think critically is one of the most important competencies that students should have. Before we talk about ways to develop critical thinking skills, let's talk about what thinking is. Thinking is carried out during the lesson, students can ask questions, interpret and analyze the topics they encounter, and expand their knowledge to a new field during the

discussion [2]. Thinking is a psychological process of thinking or reasoning to solve a problem. The term critical thinking has been studied by many Uzbek scientists and its meaning has been revealed, and several definitions are given in the "Explanatory Dictionary of Pedagogy": "Critical thinking is the given ideas (information) perceive the existence of ideas (information) that deviate from the circle and achieve this; creating new dimensions in expanding information on the subject; searching for relevant problems and finding their optimal solutions. Critical thinking is a complex thinking process that begins with assimilation of information and ends with conclusion. Critical thinking is a very important symbol of an open and democratic society. Critical thinking is the process of turning ideas and possibilities into a complex creative whole, changing the essence of information and concepts, and re-observing them. Critical thinking is a complex thinking process. Critical thinking is the result of a properly structured pedagogical process, in which the goal of teaching is to develop critical thinking. Critical thinking is the presence of ideas that deviate from the scope of given ideas; see new dimensions in the topic; the distinction between problem-solving and problem-solving, as well as between ideas expressed in argumentative writing or discussion" [2]. Critical thinking is an activity that is learned in an integrated way with educational processes and everyday life.

World scientists have also conducted a lot of research on the skill of critical thinking and give their personal views on its role in the educational process. According to E.A. Khodos and Butenko: "Critical thinking - as a set of metacognitive skills, looks for logical errors, studies the basis of knowledge, identifies hidden assumptions and misconceptions, stereotypes, forms alternative ways to solve dilemmas (problems) also evaluates the correctness and reliability of judgments" [3]. Psychologists R. Ennis and E. Norris conducted deep and conditional studies in the field of critical thinking, which they interpreted as a set of skills and abilities such as rational thinking, self-control of the thinking process, and the ability to follow laws [4]. E.M. Richard's definition of learning and thinking is based on the results of research in the field of cognitive psychology, philosophy and multimedia culture education [5].

The main results of this research are:

- ✓ The learning process will be more successful only when using different district strategies for the development of thinking activity. Such a strategy makes the learning process more conscious [6].
- ✓ Learning and critical thinking develop when students have opportunities to apply new knowledge to specific tasks[7]
- ✓ Learning is strengthened only when it relies on my student's previous knowledge and experiences. These provide an opportunity to connect students' existing knowledge with new information (Ros, 1990).
- ✓ Critical thinking and learning can be realized only when educators understand and appreciate the diversity of ideas and experiences. Critical thinking does not occur in a single-right-answer mentality.

Developing critical thinking takes time. First of all, it is necessary to get acquainted with the set of specific educational conditions and the mechanisms that help to form it.

They are:

- ✓ to give students an opportunity to think;
- ✓ acceptance of various ideas and opinions;
- ✓ ensuring the student's activity in the educational process;

✓ to convince my students that they will not be laughed at;
✓ instill a sense of confidence in each student's ability to think critically;
✓ it is necessary to appreciate the occurrence of critical thinking. Characteristics such as logical thinking, the ability to express one's thoughts freely, and not being afraid of speaking in public can also be blocked in students due to certain situations. We can observe such situations mainly in cases of blind memorization of a topic, lesson processes falling into the same pattern or situations based on memorization. The main task of applicants studying social and humanitarian sciences relies on memorizing and remembering the given information, and we observed that such students face problems with free expression of their thoughts when they enter a higher educational institution. This is exactly the kind of student

There are aspects that we pay attention to during the formation of critical thinking skills and its formation:

- to gain self-confidence and explain the value of one's opinion and ideas;
- active participation in the educational process;
- listen carefully to different opinions;
- to be ready to form their own judgments and to return from them.
- it should be explained to the students that every given opinion is very valuable and valid.

Factors necessary for the formation of critical thinking:

1. Time.
2. Permission.
3. Diversity.
4. Activity.
5. Risk taking.
6. Appreciation.
7. Value.
8. Mutual exchange of ideas[8].

Time. Critical thinking takes time. Creating one's own facts takes a certain amount of time to archeologically examine previous ideas, imaginations, encounters, and experiences. A child cannot speak immediately after birth, it takes some time for the formation of this ability, critical thinking skills are not a process that can be formed in one explanation, it takes time to adapt to it, to form one's own approach.

Permit Allowing for critical analysis is based on the principle of mindfulness. It is necessary to clarify the difference between analysis and exaggeration. Critical thinking is the process of expressing one's thoughts while respecting another person's opinion, given in a friendly and productive environment where there is a genuine purpose for thinking.

Diversity. The human mind can embody unlimited knowledge and ideas. The existence of diverse opinions and ideas belies the notion that there is a single answer. If there is only one answer, students should be taught the tools, methods, and forms of transformation used to arrive at that answer.

Activity. Critical thinking is one of the skills that requires students to be active. It is necessary to prevent students from forming the concept that only the teacher is responsible for the lesson process. Active participation of students in educational processes and arousing a sense of

responsibility for the learning process gives the expected effective result in the process of critical thinking.

Risk taking. When we are forming the ability to think freely, it is mainly based on risk-taking and during this process, it is necessary to accept as natural that unreasonable and stupid ideas can be expressed by the students, and this requires the explanation of the teacher and the pedagogue.

Appreciation. In the process of organized thinking, students respond with a sense of responsibility only when they understand that their ideas and concepts are valued by the teacher. In order to show that students appreciate their thinking process, they try to prove it to be true and begin to take its results seriously.

Expensiveness. Instilling a sense of self-confidence in each student at the beginning allows him to speak about his opinion with a steady step without any fears. People who read a lot and can analyze their works usually have a high thinking ability, their thoughts are fluent, and the words of such people are highly valued.

The process of critical thinking is a process that occurs during the exchange of controversial ideas, debates, and during these processes there is a positive competitive cooperation between students, which in turn is also the exchange of ideas. is held as

In conclusion, we can say that before improving the technology of developing students' critical thinking skills, we have considered the importance of its formation and what factors we should pay attention to in the process of its formation. The appearance of factors that shape critical thinking in future teachers can be a prelude to their steps into the future.

REFERENCES:

1. O'zbekiston Respublikasi oliy ta'lim tizimini 2030 yilgacha rivojlantirish konsepsiyasini tasdiqlash. O'zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidenti Farmoni. 2019 yil 8 oktyabr.
2. Pedagogika fanidan izohli lug'at". M.X.To'xtodjaye'vning umumiy taxriri ostida O'zbekiston respublikasi FA —"Fan" nashriyoti, Toshkent – 2008.264 b.
3. E.A.Xodos, A.V.Butenko Критическое мышление: метод, теория, практика. Moskva: "Мирос", 2002. -176b.
4. R. Ennis Evaluating Critical Thinking. New York: "Pacific Grove, CA, Widwest", 1989. -283b.
5. E.M.Richard Learning and Instruction. Upper Saddle River, N.J.: Merrill, 2003 ISBN (https://en.m.wikipedia.org/wiki/ISBN_(identifier)) 978-0-13-098396-1 (https://en.m.wikipedia.org/wiki/Special:BookSources/978-0-13-098396-1)
6. A.Palinskar. Anne.L.Brown Center for study of reading university of illinois. // Cognition and Instruction. – online nashr etilgan, 117-175b https://doi.org/10.1207/s1532690xci0102_1
7. L.B.Resnik Education and learning to think. //Creative education. –Washington, 1987.
8. N.N.Azizxo'jayeva Pedagogik texnologiyalar va pedagogik mahorat Oquv qo'llanma. - T. : "O'zbekiston yozuvchilar uyushmasi Adabiyot" jamg'armasi nashriyoti. 2006. -160b.